

NOMINATIVE - MOTIVATIONAL BASES OF TOPONYMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the morphological and syntactic formation methods of some toponyms in English and Uzbek languages. Each method is explained with examples.

INTRODUCTION

Toponyms (place names) are one of the objects of cultural wealth specific to each nation. Therefore, they are fundamentally different from other language units. So, it can be seen that toponyms are closely related not only to geography, but also to the science of linguistics. As linguistic units, they obey the same linguistic laws as all other lexemes [4,199]. However, in terms of their origin and some internal characteristics, they are of particular importance due to their connection with the daily material and spiritual condition, economic lifestyle and aspirations of the society.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Toponyms contain more ancient phonetic, lexical, and morphological elements specific to each language. Natural-geographic conditions of the place, ethnic order of the population, people's profession and occupation, mineral resources, names of the people who founded the place, historical figures and

events are the main factors in the formation of toponyms. We can see this in the example of English toponyms [1]. For example, *Aberaeron*-Mouth of the River Aeron', *Aberavon* -'Mouth of the River Afan', *Barrow* -'(place at) the wood or grove, *Docking*- 'Place where docks or water-lilies grow' (natural and geographical conditions), *Abinger*-'Enclosure of the family or followers of a man called Abba', *Ballydonohoe* -'Ó Donnchadha's townland'(person's name), *Abington*-'estate associated with a man called Abba', *Balintore*-'Village where bleaching is done', *Ballyknockan*- 'Milking place of the hillock' (profession and occupation of people).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Some toponyms may consist of a stem and word-forming suffixes, some may consist of only the stem, and others may consist of one or more words. Below we consider the morphological and syntactic formation methods of some English toponyms [1].

1. Toponyms formed by morphological (affixation) method:

-ing- + ton.

Dorrington - 'Estate associated with a man called Dēor(a)';

Dormington - 'Estate associated with a man called';

Donington, Donnington- 'Estate associated with a man called Dun(n) or Dun(n)a';

Dorsington - ('Estate associated with a man called Dēorsige');

Eardington - 'Estate associated with a man called *Earda'.

-ton.

Duncton - 'Farmstead of a man called *Dunnuca';

Dunston- 'farmstead of a man called Dun(n)';

Durston - 'Farmstead of a man called Dēor'.

-ford.

Durnford, Great - 'Hidden ford';

Wansford - 'Ford by a spring or whirlpool';

Wangford - Possibly 'ford by the open ground';

Yoxford - 'Ford wide enough for a yoke of oxen'.

-hām.

Earlham - Possibly 'homestead of a nobleman';

Earsham - Possibly 'homestead or village of a man called Ēanhere;

Eastham - 'East homestead or enclosure;

Edmondsham 'Homestead or enclosure of a man called *Ēadmōd or Ēadmund;

Walsingham, Great & Walsingham, Little - 'Homestead of the family or followers of a man called Wæls';

Walsham- 'homestead or village of a man called Walh';

Waltham- found in various counties, 'homestead or village in a forest'.

-bury.

Norbury - 'northern stronghold or manor-house';

ŪNewbury - 'New market town or borough';

Nasebury - 'Stronghold of a man called Hnæf';

Owslebury - 'Stronghold of a man called *Ōsla', or 'stronghold frequented by blackbirds'.

-by.

Usselby - 'Farmstead or village of a man called Ōswulf

Utterby - Probably 'farmstead or village of a man called Ūhtrēdor';

Enderby - 'Farmstead of a man called Eindrithi

Walesby - 'farmstead or village of a man called Valr'.

2. Syntactic method, that is, toponyms formed from more than one stem:

Noun+noun - *Edvin Loach, Egg Buckland, Eilean Donnan, Eilean Siar, Ellerdine Heath, Kyre Magna, Lach Dennis, Ladybank, Lammermuir Hills, Lossiemouth, Loughros Point, Michaelchurch, Micheldever, Milford Haven*

Noun+adjective - *Egerton Green, Elmstone Hardwicke, Littlewick Green, Llantwit Major, Loughduff, Meall Dearg, Meall Dubh, Meall Garbh, Meall Meadhonach*

Noun+preposition+noun - *Knockmealdown Mountains, Kyle Of Lochalsh, Longville in the Dale, Michaelchurch-on-Arrow, Middleton on the Hill, Monnington on Wye, Muir of Ord*

Adjective + noun - *Knotty Ash, Littlehampton, Longdon, Middlesbrough, Monadhliath Mountains, New Birmingham, New Forest, New Invention, Old Radnor.*

As can be seen from the above examples, English toponyms, like other language lexemes, have many different ways of formation. We have focused only on specific toponyms here. To list all the

English toponyms one by one will definitely take a long time and at the same time hard work.

Each toponym has its own meaning. It is no exaggeration to say that each of them has a special history, a special culture, the lifestyle of the people living there, and a great past that goes back thousands of centuries. After all, no matter what language or nationality it is, the name of each place, that is, toponyms, which are

characteristic of that nation, although they look like a common noun, hide the dreams, hopes, past and present, national culture.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that toponyms are formed and polished over several years and become a legacy for future generations. Preserving this heritage, understanding their essence, preserving old ones, forming new ones - all this is closely related to the people living in this place.

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